

1 **Deubiquitinases are active during TE lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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8 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
9 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Uchl1
10 and Usp3 as lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem
11 cells of the human embryo. Zranb2 was expressed in human ES (iPS) cells and its expression was not
12 affected by TE commitment.

13 Citations

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1. Buckley, S.M., Aranda-Orgilles, B., Strikoudis, A., Apostolou, E., Loizou, E., Moran-Crusio, K.,
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